

Studies in Terpenes. Part XLVIII. H n.m.r. Scrutiny of *p*-Mentha-1,5-diene—Maleic Anhydride Adduct and its Lactonic Acid

BAKTHAN SINGARAM and JAMES VERGHESE

Department of Chemistry, Christian Medical College, Vellore 632002

Manuscript received 15 December 1976, accepted 22 March 1977

Condensation of (-)-*p*-mentha-1,5-diene (α -phellandrene) (1) with maleic anhydride gives (-)-(1R, 2R, 3S, 4S, 5R)-7-isopropyl-5-methylbicyclo (2.2.2) oct-5-ene-2,3-dicarboxylic anhydride (4). The lactonic acid derived from the adduct is identified as (-)-(1R, 2R, 3S, 4S, 5R, 7R)-9-iso-propyl-6-methyl-4-oxo-5-oxatricyclo (4.3.1.0³⁷) decane-2-carboxylic acid (8a).

P-MENTHA-1,5-diene (α -phellandrene) (1) reacts with maleic anhydride to give an adduct represented by the plane formula (2).¹⁻⁶ The treatment of (2) with methanolic and ethanolic hydrogen chloride affords the monomethyl and monoethyl esters and these are represented by structures (3b) and (3c) respectively on the basis of their reactivity towards alkali.⁷ An alternate route to (3b) is by esterification of the hydrolysate (3a) of the adduct with diazomethane.⁸

Theoretically, the 1:4-addition product of maleic anhydride to (1) may be accommodated by the structures (4-7). In the light of the recent ¹H n.m.r. studies on the bicyclo (2.2.2) octane derivatives,^{9, 10} it is of interest to examine the stereochemistry of the adduct and of its derivatives.

Reaction of (1) and maleic anhydride in acetone gives a homogenous (t.l.c.) 1:1 adduct,⁴ m. p. 126-127°. Its molecular formula (C₁₄H₁₈O₃) is established by analytical and mass spectral data. The i.r. spectrum has the typical bands for succinic anhydride at 1850, and 1775 cm⁻¹ together with olefinic absorption at 830 cm⁻¹.

In the ¹H n.m.r. spectrum, the isopropyl methyls resonate as a pair of doublets at δ 0.81 and 0.90 and the vinyl methyl as a doublet at δ 1.76 (J 1.5Hz). Signals for C-2 and C-3 methine protons, which are coupled with each other as well as the bridgehead protons, C-1 and C-4 respectively, appear as a pair of dissymmetric doublet of doublets centred at δ 3.1 (J_{2,3}=9, J_{1,2}=J_{3,4}=3Hz). C-6 olefinic proton is visible as a doublet (J_{1,6} 6Hz) broadened by allylic couplings with the bridgehead protons and the vinyl methyl. The allylic coupling constant, J_{4,6}=J_{6,1,3}=1.5Hz, is expected of a methyl substituted bicyclo(2.2.2) olefin since increased electron density at the double bond is known to lead to large allylic coupling constants.¹¹

Molecular models indicate that only in the *endo*-isomers (4) and (5), the methyl and vinylic protons fall in the shielding cone of the rigidly held anhydride carbonyls.¹² This is reflected in the chemical shifts of the vinyl methyl and olefinic protons cited above, the usual values being δ 1.80¹³ and 5.38 to 6.49¹⁴ respectively. Further support for the *endo*-configuration is provided by the lactonisation of the dicarboxylic acid obtained by hydrolysis of the adduct (vide *infra*).

If the adduct is represented as (4), then it can reasonably account for the anisochrony of the isopropyl methyls referred to earlier. In this structure, C-10 methyl may reside mostly, probably due to restricted rotation, in the shielding cone of the 5,6-double bond.¹² This non-equivalence of the isopropyl methyls is less marked in the ¹H n.m.r. spectrum of the derived lactone (8a) in which they form a triplet around δ 0.9 (vide *infra*). Here the chemical shift difference is predictably low. On the other hand, one would not expect, in the alternative structure (5), any significant change in the relative position of the isopropyl signals when the double bond is annihilated by lactonisation; the double bond, being far away, will not influence the methyl resonances appreciably. Moreover, we can reject structure (5) on the score that its formation requires attack of the dienophile from the more hindered side of the parent hydrocarbon.

Upon mild hydrolysis of the adduct with water, the adduct affords a lactonic acid; this again supports the *endo*-configuration.¹⁵ From the spectral properties we assign structure (8a) for this derivative. The i.r. maximum at 1770 cm⁻¹ indicates a ν -lactone.^{18, 15, 16} In the ¹H n.m.r. spectrum the C-6 methyl group appears as a singlet at δ 1.42. No signal occurs downfield from δ 3.0 except the carboxylic proton which resonates as a broad singlet at δ 10.12. This reveals the involvement of C-5 carbon rather than C-6

carbon atom in the lactone formation. The C-2 and C-3 methine protons constitute an AB pattern (J 10Hz); here the downfield signal centred at δ 2.92 is split further into a doublet through coupling with C-7 bridgehead proton ($J_{8,7}$ 5Hz) which is located at 2.28 as a multiplet. When the spectrum is scanned with simultaneous irradiation of the signal at δ 2.28, the C-3 proton quartet collapses to a doublet ($J_{2,3}$ 10Hz). For the adduct we have seen that the $J_{3,4}$ is 3 Hz; in the bicyclo(2.2.2) octane system, the $J_{2,3}$ value of 2,3-dicarboxylic acid is 12Hz.¹⁰ In the derived lactonic acid, the $J_{2,3}$ and $J_{3,4}$ are 10Hz and 5Hz respectively. This implies that during lactonisation the molecule has rotated on the C-1, C-4 axis.¹⁷ The increase in $J_{1,2}$ from 3 (dihedral angle $\sim 55^\circ$) to 5Hz corresponds to an increase in the H(2)-H(3) dihedral angle to $\sim 25^\circ$; these changes in dihedral angles are in accord with the C-3 carbonyl group moving away from the nearest ethylenic bridge.¹⁷ The multiplet at δ 2.28 is assigned to C-7 proton; this resonance merges with that of C-1 proton and the C-10 proton *exo* to the carboxylic function. Decoupling experiments support these assignments and show that the C-10¹ proton *endo* to the carboxylic acid group falls at

group to relieve the interaction and points to a H(7)-H(8) dihedral angle of $\sim 37^\circ$.¹⁷

We further confirmed the structure of the lactonic acid by examining its methyl and ethyl esters, which are represented by formulae (8b) and (8c) respectively on the basis of the ¹Hn.m.r. features (see Experimental section). For both (8b) and (8c), the C-6 methyl appears as a singlet at δ 1.42. The ¹H n.m.r. spectrum of the methyl ester is identical with that of (8a), except for the singlet at δ 3.68 assignable to the ester methyl.

It is concluded therefore that the absolute configuration of the adduct (4) is 1R, 2R, 3S, 4S, 5R, while that of (8a), (8b), and (8c) is 1R, 2R, 3S, 4S, 5R, 7R.

Experimental

For general directions see reference 18. ¹Hn.m.r. spectra were taken with a Varian A-100 spectrometer in CDCl₃ with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Mass spectra were run at 70 ev with samples being introduced at 100°.

(1)

(2)

(3)

- (a) R=H
(b) R=Me
(c) R=Et

(4)

(5)

δ 1.67 as a broadened doublet (J_{AB} 14Hz). The long-range coupling of this proton with C-9 methine proton results only in broadening of the signal. C-8¹ proton appears as a pair of quartet centered at δ 1.98 (J_{AB} 13, $J_{8,9}$ 6 and $J_{7,8}$ 5Hz). Irradiation of the multiplet at δ 1.2 attributed to C-8, C-9 and C-11 protons tickles the C-8¹ signal into a doublet ($J_{7,8}$ 5Hz). The $J_{7,8}$ value reveals again that the isopropyl group has receded from the bridge methyl

(1R, 2R, 3S, 4S, 5R)-7-Isopropyl-5-methylbicyclo-(2.2.2)oct-5-ene-2, 3-dicarboxylic anhydride (4).—The adduct (4) was prepared following the directions of Goodway and West⁴ m.p. 126-127° (lit.,⁴ 126°, R_f 0.70, $(\alpha)_D^{20} = 11.30$ (c 8.2 in CHCl₃) (Found: C, 71.6; H, 7.8. C₁₄H₁₈O₈ requires C, 71.8; H, 7.7%), ν_{max} 3060 (—C=C str.), 1870, 1850, 1838, 1775 (C=O anhydride), 1650 (C=C), 1240 (C-O-C str.), and 830 cm⁻¹ (trisubstituted C=C), m/e 234 (M⁺,

8%), 206 (12), 164 (13), 93 (25), 92 (100), 91 (30), 78 (26), and 41 (12).

(1R, 2R, 3S, 4S, 5R, 7R)-9-Isopropyl-6-methyl-4-oxo-5-oxatricyclo (4.3.1.0^{3,7}) decane-2-carboxylic acid (8~).—The method of Augestad was used⁶. The product had m.p. 170° (lit.⁸, 170°), R_f 0.67, (α)_D²⁰ —41.6° (c 3.2 in CHCl₃) (Found : C, 66.5 ; H, 8.1.

10H, and 10'H), 1.04 (3H, s, 6-Me), 0.90 (3H, m, 8-H, 9-H, and 11-H) and 0.67 and 0.57 (6H, d, J 7Hz, isopropyl).

(1R, 2R, 3S, 4S, 5R, 7R)-2-Carboethoxy-9-isopropyl-6-methyl-4-oxo-5-oxatricyclo (4.3.1.0^{3,7}) decane (8c)—This derivative was obtained by the known method,⁷ m.p. 98° (lit., ⁷98°), R_f 0.80 (α)_D²⁰ —19.3° (c 4.2 in CHCl₃) (Found : C, 68.9 ; H, 8.2.

(6)

(7)

(8)

- (a) R=H
(b) R=Me
(c) R=Et

C₁₄H₂₀O₄ requires C, 66.6 ; H, 8.0%), ν_{max} 1770 (ν -lactone), 1710 (C=O acid), 1450 (C-H-str.), 1380, 1375 (isopropyl), and 1220 cm⁻¹ (C-O str.).

(1R, 2R, 3S, 4S, 5R, 7R)-2-Carbomethoxy-9-isopropyl-6-methyl-4-oxo-5-oxatricyclo (4.3.1.0^{3,7}) decane (8b).—The esterification was carried out after the manner of Goodway and West,⁷ m.p. 105-106° (lit.,⁷ 105°), R_f 0.70, (α)_D²⁰ —20.2° (c 2.8 in CHCl₃)

(Found : C, 67.3 ; H, 8.5. C₁₅H₂₂O₄ requires C, 67.7 ; H, 8.3%), ν_{max} 1770 (ν -lactone), 1735 (C=O ester), 1380, 1375 (isopropyl), 1240 and 1080cm⁻¹ (C-O str.), δ 3.68 (s, 3H, ester Me), 2.86 (1H, q, J_{2,3} 10, J_{3,7} 5Hz, 3-H), 2.66 (1H, q, J_{2,3} 10, J_{3,10} 1Hz, 2-H), 2.20 (3H, m, 1-H, 7-H, and 10-H), 1.98 (1H, dq, J_{8,8'} 14, J_{9',9} 9, J_{7,8'} 5Hz, 8'-H), 1.65 (1H, q, J_{10,10'} 15, J_{9,10'} 1Hz, 10'-H), 1.42 (3H, s, 6-Me), 1.20 (3H, m, 8-H, 9-H and 11-H), and 0.90 (6H, t, J 7Hz, isopropyl), δ (C₆D₆) 3.52 (3H, s, ester Me), 2.58 (1H, q, J_{2,3} 10, J_{3,7} 5Hz, 3-H), 2.28 (1H, q, J_{2,3} 10, J_{3,10} 1Hz, 2-H), 2.00br (1H, s, W₃ 9Hz, 1-H), 1.58 (1H, q, J_{3,7} 5, J_{7,8} 4.5Hz, 7-H), 1.30 (3H, m, 8'-H,

C₁₆H₂₄O₄ requires C, 68.5 ; H, 8.6%), ν_{max} 1770 (ν -lactone), 1730 (C=O ester), 1385, 1375 (isopropyl) 1240 and 1080 cm⁻¹ (C-O str.), δ 4.13 (1H, q, J 7Hz, -O-CH₂-), 2.86 (1H, q, J_{2,3} 10, J_{3,7} 5Hz, 3-H), 2.66 (1H, q, J_{2,3} 10, J_{3,10} 1Hz, 2-H), 2.20 (3H, m, 1-H, 7-H, and 10-H), 1.98 (1H, dq, J_{8,8'} 14, J_{8',9} 9, J_{7,8'} 5Hz, 8'-H), 1.64 (1H, q, J_{10,10'} 15, J_{10',9} 1Hz, 10'-H), 1.42 (3H, s, 6-Me), 1.23 (3H, t, J 7Hz, CH₃-CH₂-) and 0.90 (6H, t, J 1Hz, isopropyl).

Acknowledgement

We thank Drs. C. N. Pillai, Dr. Nasipuri and G. Mehta, for their helpful comments and suggestions during the preparation of this paper and Dr., J. M. Bruce for the ¹H n. m. r. spectra.

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